

Anekāntavāda: A special Jain Episteme, Which can Shun Monoculturalism and Monolithic Understanding of the World

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Guiding premises

“For sin is not one mere action, it is an attitude of life which takes for granted that we are not all essentially one, but exist each for his own separate individual existence.” – Rabindranath Tagore (1861 –1941)

Reality is created by the mind; we can change our reality by changing our mind. - Plato (428/427 or 424/423 – 348 BC)

Abstract

Anekāntavāda is a special orientation of the Jain movement, which is a great attainment of the Indian *Śramaṇa* tradition through the wisdom of the Jain *Tīrthaṅkaras*. Historically it played an important role in developing human being’s gnosis and insight. It is beneficial to create an overarching *Weltanschauung* that can motivate human beings to respect others’ beliefs and philosophies and shun monoculturalism and their parochial outlooks. The lack of this knowledge might have propelled human beings to misapprehend the sentient and non-sentient worlds. This paper wants to reexamine how this great philosophy once enriched Indian culture and heritage in such a manner that till now India is the abode of the highest number of different races and their varied religious and political ideologies. And we know that without some exceptions their abreast living is a peaceful coexistence as it was previously. The paper wants to delve into the fact again and enumerate the possibility of its capacity and scope, if the modern world wants to glean strategic benefit from it. The paper wants to reassess its ability to establish ‘global peace’ and change the monolithic prejudiced attitudes of people across the world.

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Introduction

Modern knowledge has a tendency to adopt the ancient understanding of the world. The reason is tangible; the ancient wisdoms and perceptions can be revised and regenerated to get outstanding outputs from their application in fixing strategy and management mechanics for statecraft, institutions and enterprises. Many times, some good outcomes have been yielded. The modern strategists are always the admirers of the War strategy of Sun Tzu (771–256 BC), a Chinese military general, philosopher and writer. He lived during the Eastern Zhou period. His masterpiece ‘the Art of War’ is still considered very relevant and worthy to be applied for military purposes. Chanakya (375 BCE – 283 BCE), a great Indian sage and polymath, also identified as Kauṭilya or Vishnugupta, was an advisor of the first Mauryan emperor Chandragupta Maurya and played a significant role to expand his empire successfully. He was also a great economist, strategist and political thinker. Chanakya served as the chief advisor to both Emperors Chandragupta and his son Bindusara. His book “*Arthashastra*” uplifted the quality of political science, economic policy and military strategy of the ancient India. Not only India and the Indians and other Asian secular and semi-secular intellectuals and scholars contributed to the practical arenas of knowledge, but also the spiritual mentors and leaders across the whole Asia. The Jain *Tīrthaṅkaras* played foremost roles in this regard. A lot of issues can be explored of the Jain knowledge and heritage, if I want to mention their contributions. Jain time cycle, architecture, logical understanding of the world, methodology to deduce and come upon logical solutions regarding various issues and subject matters - all are praiseworthy and remarkable.

Through their writings the Jains have enriched not only the ancient languages such as Sanskrit, Prakrit and Apabhramsa, but also many modern Indian languages, namely, Hindi, Gujarati, Marathi, Kannada, Tamil and Telugu.

We have known that a huge amount of this vast Jain literature continues to be stored in innumerable Jain temples and *Shastra bhandaras*, and remains unclassified and unpublished as yet (Bhargava 1968 : 226-55). Those should be explored meticulously.

Moris Winternitz (1863-1937), a renowned Indologist once opined that the contribution to languages and literature by the Jains is quite remarkable and praiseworthy. (Winternitz, 1946)

The Jain literature covers vast extent of knowledge world:

- a) *The Puranas* i.e. the mythology and legend oriented sacred literature,
- b) *The Charitiras* the characters and personas of important personalities,
- c) *The Katha* i.e. the stories,
- d) *The Prabandha* i.e. the essays,
- e) *The Kāvya*s i.e. the poems, and
- f) *The Mahākāvya*s i.e. the epics

All of the above fall within its ambit. It includes scientific as well as technical knowledge like astronomy, astrology and cosmology.

Simultaneously the Jains significantly contributed into the realms of mathematics, geography, economics, grammar, logic, philosophy, poetics, lexicography and so forth. One of the major interests of the Jains in this vast literature is to overcome the mundane misery and sufferings not only through rituals and conventions, but also through good moral deeds and self-correction.

The *Anekāntavāda* has been portrayed significantly with most of the above-mentioned precious gems of the Jain world. It correlated among the Jain logic, philosophy, cosmology, phenomenology, eschatology and soteriology.

We know that Jain epistemology developed on Triple “A”.

- *Anekāntavāda*
- *Aparigraha*
- *Ahimsa*

Actually, this Triple “A” play the propellers of all Jain knowledge oriented factors i.e. the Jain episteme, and finally the Jain philosophy and the Jain universe could embarked upon a gnosis to enrich humanity with a rationality, which bases holistically and give us an intelligible and very meaningful soteriology. However, it has some deeper meaning and significance, which is beyond the extent of the commoners and the ordinary minds.

Philosophically we can show the linear process of the Jain soteriology in the following way:

Knowledge from the known and the unknown worlds by applying the pure sense of cosmology + scrutiny through the lens of logic + understanding the outcomes with objective and rational perspectives through philosophical judgment especially by phenomenology and ontology = Jain soteriology

The goal of the above process is to be exempt from the Karmic bondage and attain the *Moksha*.

Here *Ahimsa* and *Aparigraha* help the omniscient man or the *Arihant* to develop inside *Anekāntavāda* and vice versa. If he is the elevated *Tīrthaṅkara*, with his own salvation he leads the path not only for the mankind but also for all the sentient and non-sentient beings for a *collective salvation*. But in the meantime, he opens the eyes of people through the real understanding of the universe and truth by means of *Anekāntavāda*. The *Arihants* and the *Tīrthaṅkaras* literally nullify the sense and judgmental attitude of monoculturalism, prejudiced rationality, religious bigotry and extremism. So, this paper wants to check the psychological, strategic and organizational benefits, if we pursue *Anekāntavāda* in order to establish global peace. I want to show that the philosophy of *Anekāntavāda* has an obvious and conspicuous ability to bring forth peace globally. It also retains an underlying motivational force to change our monolithic understanding of the world and our prejudiced attitudes. Our reality is self-derived and self-driven; *Anekāntavāda* can change it and transform us.

How logic and rationality construe the path towards *Anekāntavāda* in Jainism

Anekāntavāda has unveiled a profound truth, which was mainly and primarily propagated by the Jain *Tīrthaṅkaras*. The ultimate truth or reality is complex and unintelligible for the commoners because of its esoteric metaphysical existence. It has enshrouded the world in a varied and complex manner that the sentient and non-sentient beings that exist here cannot fathom it perfectly and entirely with their capacity of perceptibility. Therefore, reality appears here in many aspects. But we cannot or should not override anyone's belief or philosophy considering that to be banal or parochial as like them we all are finite beings. Any single statement or doctrinal proposition must retain the pitfalls to fathom the universe and reality. And it will be a parochial attitude to impose the understanding of someone upon another as we all are living with our limited understandings. The Jains believe that only he who has attained the *kevala jnana* i.e. the *Kaivalya* is an omniscient person, could develop his ability to understand the ultimate truth and the ultimate reality. So, it deals seriously with ontology and phenomenology. This premise has developed the basic philosophy of Jainism and its initial introduction that motivate us to know the Jain *Arihants* and the *Tīrthaṅkaras* and we can embark upon *Anekāntavāda*. Here we can remind that:

- a. *An Arihant decides his own destiny, but a Tīrthaṅkara decides for all. An Arihant is omniscient. But a Tīrthaṅkara is omnipotent, who has already attained the level of omniscience and has become something more.*
- b. *An Arihant is conscious of his bondage and concerned for his liberation. He can liberate himself. As a Tīrthaṅkara is omnipotent, he is well competent to liberate himself and*

the whole universe as well. He is the liberator of both sentient and non sentient beings, conscious and unconscious.

Rationally we also need someone who knows the universe infiltrating our three-dimensional tangibility and perceptibility. We are encrusted with this three-dimensional tangibility and existing as 'finite beings'. We think that we know the universe, although we don't know even an iota. We are limited from a wider phenomenological perspective as we know some limited phenomena of the universe. The *Arihants* and the *Tīrthaṅkaras* are not limited. They have infiltrated this crust of three dimensions. What they did has a very logical conclusion that the Indian sages fathomed after their pensive enquiries through thousands of years.

Glancing on *Pratītyasamutpāda* philosophy of Buddhism, anchoring on *Anekāntavāda* – marching towards strategic benefit for peace.

When we realize that the reality we realize is due to our limited perceptibility is very shallow, we also come to the conclusion that the world we perceive is '*Mayik*' i.e. illusory. The *Maya* prevents people from embracing the reality within the ultimate cosmological, ontological and phenomenological spectra. The Jain says that the right belief i.e. '*Samyaktva*' can help us to know that to some extent. It at least propels people to jump over false beliefs – '*Mithyatva*'. We can compare it with Plato's depiction of his famous '*allegory of cave*'. In a shadowy world, the prisoners are realizing the reality from the obscurant phenomena. They create their own world depending upon this reality and discern everything depending on it. Jainism says that these limited and parochial beliefs and understandings also motivate to long for mundane pleasure and glory – '*Nidana*'. It brings forth '*Kashaya*' or passion in us, which is the generator of all judgmental understandings and perceptions that also creates *aham* and *maan* i.e. ego in us and all sentient beings. The peril of bigotry and monolithic belief emerges from it and the '*Pandora's box*' becomes open. The self-destructive as well as the world destructive monster gets unleashed. However, an *Arihant* is an over-conscious being, who knows what he perceives is beyond the capacity or ability of the commoners. He also realizes that if it is to discard one school of philosophy, all schools will be eliminated automatically. The ideologies anyway all are some deliberate processes to go to humanity. From this perspective, all ideologies are true from a partial understanding. An object can be observed from many angles; the many perspectives would be experienced and perceived. All are true from their certain (limited) perspectives and propositions.

Pic: An object has many sides; anybody can see only one side or some can more, only the Arihant can see all sides and absolutely ‘the whole’.

However, the limited understandings do at least minimal welfare for the society for a certain period as all the ideologues and philosophers are some great sages and great minds. This is the connotation of *Anekāntavāda*.

Hence, we can take a look at *Pratītyasamutpāda* philosophy from the Buddhist understanding. The very term *Pratītyasamutpāda* means ‘dependent origination.’ It means all new philosophies and ideas are the result of concatenation. From the religious point of view, the new denominations emerge from the previous ones. In fact it depicts the chain of causality of material and non-material functions and phenomena.

Can we smell the *Hegelian dialectic* here; I mean the chain of *Thesis-Antithesis and Synthesis*. It can be, because “*wise men think alike*”. The great Hindu adage: “*Ekam Sat Vipra Bahudha Vadanti*.” — “That which exists is One: sages call it by various names.”

Does it also reveal *Anekāntavāda*? Yes, the *Tīrthāṅkaras* posit that one thing can be observed and one idea or statement can be manifested differently by different people. Ramakrishna Paramahansa (1836–1886), the great Bengali sage and mystic, echoed the same thing through his assertion: “*Joto mot toto Path*”- so many doctrines, so many paths.

Although it is limited from the sight of an Arihant and a *Tīrthāṅkara* no doubt, it has also a certain strategic benefit. Different people have different tastes, proclivity or ways to accept the truth. The philosophy of *Tīrthāṅkaras* recognizes them all as people of different time and space understand the reality from their limited cognizance, tangibility and perceptibility. The more complexity cannot be attained and sustained by them. Rather, the limited vision and cognizance at least can ensure a ‘*status quo*’ for people and ‘*modus vivendi*’

can be sustained for regional peace and also for the global; which is a limited idea of peaceful coexistence, but better than none.

Aparigraha and *Ahimsā* for the Jains – who can herald the global peace

The above-mentioned strategy can be sufficient for others and for the time being; not for the Jain theologians and philanthropists. They certainly committed to do something more. The Jain monks and the philanthropists are fortunate to be influenced by the domino effect of the works done by the *Tīrthaṅkaras*. They have already learnt that this known world is superficial and perfunctory and also transient. The Karmic phenomena have immersed them into illusion and delusion at a time. The *Tīrthaṅkaras* have delivered three great instruments to the disciples; a) *Anekāntavāda*, b) *Aparigraha*, and c) *Ahimsā*

pic: The pyramid of triple “A”, the instruments of attaining Nirvana

In fact *Anekāntavāda*, *Aparigraha* and *Ahimsā* are synergetic for one another. They enrich one another’s faculty and capacity.

We know that *Aparigraha* is the virtue of non-possessiveness, non-grasping, or non-greediness as we have no intention to have anything from this superficial reality and to fall under the servitude of the Karmic bondage. As we are oriented to this profound understanding, we will feel the harm of *Hiṃsā* or desire to be violent against anybody and will teach *Ahimsā* i.e. non-violence. From now on we will feel pity for all sentient beings and strong eagerness to guide them. However, it is to be noted that the Jain doctrines of relativity do not represent the form of *relativism* from the western viewpoint. A fully sighted person i.e. an omniscient Jina /a liberated great teacher and also one who has overcome his ego and conquered self and the universe is certainly capable of apprehending the true nature of anything. This is very different from the usual western relativism, which is deeply skeptical about the ability of a human being. The Western philosophy casts doubt if a human being really knows anything with certainty.

The omnipotent *Tīrthaṅkaras* ensure the fluxes of change. They can do that from their metaphysical stream and they actuate that among their followers. The number of *Tīrthaṅkaras* is fixed in every time cycle and that is 24. In Jain cosmology, the wheel of time is divided into two halves, the ascending time cycle is called *Utsarpiṇī*, and the descending *half is Avasarpiṇī*. The *Tīrthaṅkaras* appear in the third and fourth quarters of the both halves. They also indoctrinate to create *Jain Sangha* i.e. the Jain community and activate the Spiritual hierarchy to promote the personal spiritual goal and the global peace. The hierarchy can be sketched nowadays as follows:

1. **Arihant:** We have talked about the Arhants. They are the awakened souls who have attained *Kevala Jñana* or absolute knowledge.
2. **Siddha :** They are the souls and beings, who have been liberated from the birth and death cycle. They are also those, who have attained *Siddhi* i.e. the power of performing paranormal capabilities (White, Dominik 2012: 34).
3. **Ācārya:** An *Ācārya* is the head of the ascetic order. Some of the noted *Achāryas* are Bhadrabahu, Kundakunda, Samantabhadra, Umaswami, Sthulibhadra etc.
4. **Upadhyaya:** An Upadhyaya is a preceptor or a teacher, who perceives and then teaches to enlighten his pupils.

We know that the Jain monasticism refers to the Jain *Munis* of major denominations: the Digambara and the *Śvētāmbara* and also others. They teach *Aparigraha*, *Ahimsā* and *Anekāntavāda*. They also simultaneously teach Satya (Truth), *Asteya* (Non-stealing), and Brahmacharya (Chastity). They help the people to unlearn violence and teach to be nonviolent. The Jain Relativism emerged from the *Anekāntavāda* will cultivate the mentality to accept all in the human mind. Historically we could embark upon a second doctrine, *Nayavāda* from the trail of *Anekāntavāda*. It is named the ‘*doctrine of perspectives*’ by Jeffery D Long. This is an epistemic corollary of the first one – the nature of knowledge complex in the complex universe; it resonates with the *Anekāntavāda*’s point. As the nature of reality is complex, anything may be known from a variety of *Nayas* or perspectives, which correspond to its multiple aspects. Hence this finally implies the third doctrine – *Syādvāda* or the ‘*doctrine of conditional prediction*’ (named by D Long, which literally means the ‘*maybe doctrine*’). According to this doctrine the truth of any claim that one makes about a particular topic is dependent upon the related perspective, or *Naya*, from which the claim has been made. A claim can be true in one sense or from one perspective (the technical meaning of the Sanskrit verb ‘*Syāt*’ from the Jain philosophical context), false from another perspective, both true and false

from another, although it may have an inexpressible truth-value from yet another etc (D Long 2009: 117). So, *Anekāntavāda* is very accommodative for all perspectives; but drives the pensive minds to the higher plane of rationality and decisions. Its philanthropic attitude can shun egoistic monoculturism and the audacity of the ‘*Realpolitik*’ propagated by Hans Joachim Morgenthau (1904-1980) and his predecessors like Niccolò Machiavelli (1469 - 1527) and Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679). This political realism with its cardinal engine Real Politik has influenced people to be self-centered and the modern man has become *homo economicus*. This philosophy has given human beings the excuse to be egoistic and selfish as these are rational to survive on this planet according to this doctrine. So, the occupation of other territories and plundering other lands are justified by this. *Anekāntavāda* can be a global panacea against this.

Concluding remarks through the propositions:

The Jains have to work globally to promote *Anekāntavāda* with two objectives.

1. They should disseminate their philosophy and literature across the world. We know *Tattvārthasūtra*, which is a quasi-canonical text, developed on the basis of *Anekāntavāda* written in Sanskrit by Ācārya Umaswami between 2nd to 5th centuries CE. The Jains should write more basing upon *Anekāntavāda* like this one relating the present world’s scenarios.
2. The Jains can propose the UNO and other Supranational and International organizations to accept *Anekāntavāda* as a philosophical maxim for their peace mission and propagate it as a great sagacity and global heritage to establish a “*meaningful and sustainable global peaceful order*”.

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